

both as Nujol and hexachlorobutadiene mulls were recorded in the region 5000-650 cm^{-1} using a Unicam SP-200 double beam spectrophotometer with rock salt optics.

Results and Discussion

The imidazole nucleus and derivatives thereof are known to play extremely crucial role in the structure and functioning of a number of biologically important molecules, generally by virtue of their being coordinated to the metal ion. The interaction of imidazole with several metal ions has been studied⁴⁻⁶ and the coordination through the tertiary (pyridine) nitrogen has been confirmed by X-ray structural studies⁷. The complexes now reported behave as 1 : 1 electrolytes (Table 1).

The infrared spectral data are quite informative. The (N-H) bending and stretching frequencies of the free I_2 were observed at 1460 and 2935, 3255 cm^{-1} ⁸ and that of $2\text{M}_e\text{I}_2$ at 1458 and 2750 cm^{-1} respectively. In the spectrum of $[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3\text{N}][\text{CdBr}_3(\text{I}_2)_2]$, the $\delta(\text{N-H})$ is shifted to a lower frequency at 1422 cm^{-1} and $\nu(\text{N-H})$ is raised to 3100, 3300 and 3500 cm^{-1} . Similar observation of lowering of $\delta(\text{N-H})$ and raising of $\nu(\text{N-H})$ was noticed in case of the complex $[\text{Et}_3\text{N}][\text{CdBr}_3(2\text{-M}_e\text{-I}_2)]$. In the complex $[\text{Et}_3\text{N}][\text{CdI}_3(2\text{-M}_e\text{-I}_2)]$, while the $\nu(\text{N-H})$ band occurs in the higher range, the $\delta(\text{N-H})$ remained unchanged. In the complex $[\text{Et}_3\text{N}][\text{CdI}_3(\text{IQ})_2]$, the bands attributable to free isoquinoline, have been modified showing that it is bonded to the metal ion. Further the absorption bands at 800, 1010, 1065, 1180 cm^{-1} attributable to the tetraethyl ammonium cation are also observed in the infrared spectra of all the complexes.

Imidazole ($p^ka=7$) is less basic than its 2-methyl derivative ($p^ka=8.3$)^{9,10}. Hence an increase in coordination number is expected with I_2 compared to $2\text{-M}_e\text{I}_2$ which is substantiated in the present investigation (Table 1). When isoquinoline is used as a ligand, a penta-coordinated anionic $[\text{CdI}_3(\text{IQ})_2]^-$ complex is formed. Thus the preferred coordination number appears to be different with different ligands. In general, cadmium(II) ion in tetra-, penta- and hexa-coordinated complexes, uses respectively the $5s$ $5p^3$, $5s$ $5p^2$ $5d$ and $5s$ $5p^2$ $5d^2$ hybrid orbitals for bonding. Whilst the tetra- and hexa-coordinated complexes prefer tetrahedral and octahedral forms respectively, the geometry of the penta-coordinated one can be decided only by X-ray studies.

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Mixed Ligand Complexes of Mn(II) and Cd(II) Dithiocarbamates with Nitrogen Donors

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ZINC diethyl dithiocarbamate and other dithiocarbamates have been used as accelerators for vulcanising rubbers and as potential fungicides. Even though dithiocarbamates of Mn(III), Mn(II) and other divalent transition metals have been reported earlier, mixed ligand complexes containing both sulfur and nitrogen atoms have not been studied. In an earlier communication⁵ mixed ligand zinc(II) dithiocarbamate complexes have been reported. It was thought worthwhile to extend the investigation to the case of Cd(II) and Mn(II) dithiocarbamate and this communication describes a number of mixed ligand Mn(I) and Cd(II) dithiocarbamate complexes with nitrogen donors.

All the chemicals used were of Analar grade. Diethyl dithiocarbamates were prepared by earlier known³⁻⁴ methods. Mn(II) dithiocarbamate is susceptible to aerial oxidation. Hence this was immediately treated with absolute ethanol and amines in 1 : 2 ratio and refluxed for thirty minutes. Cd(II) dithiocarbamate was reacted in a similar manner. On cooling crystalline compounds were separated out. These were filtered under suction, washed with ethanol, followed by ether and dried in a vacuum desiccator. Metal and sulfur were estimated by standard methods and nitrogen by microanalysis. Conductance was measured in

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF Mn(II) AND Cd(II) COMPLEXES

Compounds	M.P. (°C)	Λ_M (mhos. cm ²)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	%metal		%sulfur		%nitrogen	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
MnL ₂ (β -pic) ₂	186	8.2	5.92	9.85	10.23	23.62	23.84	10.24	10.58
MnL ₂ Q ₂	198	9.4	5.95	8.91	9.02	20.82	21.02	8.82	9.2
MnL ₂ (Morph) ₂	215	8.6	5.95	10.22	10.47	24.11	24.39	10.35	10.67
CdL ₂ (β -pic)	7250	10.5	—	22.14	22.42	25.31	25.54	8.02	8.38
CdL ₂ Q	200	10.8	—	20.69	20.91	23.62	23.82	7.61	7.82
CdL ₂ (Morph.)	238	11.6	—	22.34	22.69	25.56	25.83	8.16	8.48
CdL ₂ Py	212	11.8	—	22.34	22.05	26.05	26.26	8.48	8.62

β -pic= β -picoline, Q=quinoline, Py=Pyridine, Morph=Morpholine.

$\frac{M}{1000}$ acetone solution, I.R. spectra were recorded in KBr phase in Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra of Mn(II) complexes were studied using $\frac{M}{100}$ acetone solution using Hilger Watt Uvispek spectrophotometer. Relevant data are recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

All the Mn(II) complexes have the general composition MnL₂B₂ and Cd(II) complexes are of the type CdL₂B, where L is diethyl dithiocarbamate and B is an amine viz. pyridine, β -picoline, quinoline and morpholine. These are white crystalline solids and have low molar conductance values in acetone, Λ_M being in the range of 8-12 mhos.cm² (Table 1) indicating non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. Infrared spectra of dithiocarbamates have been studied earlier by Nakamoto et al⁵ and others⁶. Important characteristic bands viz. $\nu(C-N)$ and $\nu(C-S)$ could be easily assigned. In sodium diethyl dithiocarbamate $\nu(C-N)$, $\nu_{as}(C-S)$ and $\nu_s(C-S)$ occur⁶ at 1450, 890 and 1260 cm⁻¹ respectively. In Mn(II) and Cd(II) dithiocarbamates these bands appear ~1430, 880 and 1240 cm⁻¹ respectively. Shifting of these bands to lower frequency region indicates coordination through both the sulfur atoms. In the mixed ligand complexes these bands were observed ~1450, 890 and 1250 cm⁻¹. Shifting of these bands again to higher frequency region occurs due to the coordination of σ -bonding nitrogen donor ligands. In addition, most of the free nitrogen ligand absorption are shifted in the complexes indicating bonding to the metal ion. These have been further substantiated by observation of absorption bands ~260-300 and ~350-380 cm⁻¹ region attributable⁷ to $\nu(M-S)$ and $\nu(M-N)$ vibrations. Hence on the basis of these observations cadmium complexes are presumed to be penta-coordinated. In view of the spherical nature of the Cd(II) ion and the absence of crystal field effects, this is not entirely unexpected.

Mn(II) complexes show at least four absorption bands ~18.4-18.6, 22.6-22.8, 24.4-24.5 and 27.7 k.k. regions assignable⁸ to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, $\rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$,

$\rightarrow {}^4E_g$, $A_{1g}(G)$ and $\rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(D)$ transitions respectively. A high spin octahedral structure is suggested for these complexes. Magnetic moment values of 5.9-B.M. also supports this configuration.

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Mixed Ligand Diamine Complexes of Ni(II), Cu(II) and Pd(II) with 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthaldehyde and Benzoylacetone

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A survey of the literature¹⁻³ has shown that no work has been done on the mixed ligand complexes of Ni(II), Cu(II) and Pd(II) with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and benzoylacetone. The mixed ligand complexes have been treated with diamines to get mixed diamine complexes.